

The Madness of Dashu: An “Othering” Force or a Tool for Resistance

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“A meagre frame topped by head of large size,
Like the koi fish of Jessore in human guise.” (Ray 2012,
1)

This is how one of the most iconic child characters in Bengali literature is introduced for the first time. Sukumar Ray’s seminal character Dasharathi or Dashu is a young schoolboy whose unusual looks and behaviour have earned him the title of a pagla (mad) boy in his school¹. Dashu, however, does not naively accept this label or allow the institutional structure to marginalise him². Through his antics, Dashu not only turns the order of his school upside down but also makes others question the notion of madness and the hierarchy itself. The late eighteenth and early nineteenth-century education system of Bengal was facing radical changes with the introduction of new pedagogy and numerous educational institutions. These institutions often earned criticism regarding their tendency to uphold the dominant class structure and Western ideologies. Many contemporary intellectuals such as Mahatma Gandhi, Rabindranath Tagore, and Sukumar Ray questioned the role of existing hegemonic educational structure in nourishing the imaginative mind of a child and moulding the child to

conform to popular social values and ideologies. In the humorous world of Dashu, Sukumar Ray throws light upon the institution's role as what Louis Althusser would later term Ideological State Apparatus. According to Althusser, Ideological State Apparatuses normalise the class structure and ideology of the dominant class. Being indoctrinated at a young age, people tend to follow these ideologies and submit to the hierarchies created by and for the ruling class without questioning them. They are normalised to the point that any alternate structure appears unthinkable. Ray presents Pagla Dashu as an extraordinary genius with a mind so sharp that his antics often make people question his madness. The structure of the school forms a hegemonic system that positions people in an unequal hierarchy of power. It provides the teachers, snobbish boys, know-it-alls, and sycophants with a sense of unquestionable authority over the rest. Dashu, the mad boy of the school, brings forth the arbitrariness of such a power structure. Ray was a master of portraying the nuances of contemporary socio-political issues through his humorous satires, well known for the hybrid identities and liminal positions, in celebrated works like *HajaBaRaLa* (1921), *Abol Tabol* (1923), and the like. While his approaches to hybrid identity, colonialism, and form have intrigued scholars time and again, his critique of the structure of the educational institution, politics of madness, and portrayal of the functions of schools as an Ideological State Apparatus have received lesser attention, especially these as found in stories of Pagla Dashu. One of the brilliant works addressing similar questions as this paper is Asma Ladha's article "A Hint of Madness and a Trace of Genius: A Perspective on Sukumar Ray's 'Pagla Dashu' Stories Using Foucault's History of Madness." (2014) In the article, Ladha makes some interesting claims to justify her argument that society turns Dashu into a madman and fool only to render him an example of unaccepted social behavior. Taking a different stance than Ladha, this paper aims to analyse the portrayal of Pagla Dashu, who appears mostly in five stories: "Pagla Dashu," "Chinese Crackers," "Dashu's Antics," "Dashu's Crazy Act," and "The Detective" in the collection *The Crazy Tales of Pagla Dashu and Co.* (2012), and tries to show how Ray turns

Dashu's madness into an empowering tool enabling him to question and disrupt the structure from within.

Introduced for the first time in the story "Pagla Dashu," Dasharathi, better known as Dashu, is a young schoolboy who has earned the title "mad" for both his looks and antics. However, he is not stupid but rather an unorthodox genius. The narrator mentions that his brilliance was evident when he would easily solve complicated mathematic equations or come up with unique tricks to make a fool of his friends. When Pagla (mad) Dashu is introduced in the first story, the narrator provides accounts of some incidents that not only established Dashu as the mad boy of the school but also made him the centre of attention for other schoolboys. He once tricked his friends simply by playing mind games and making use of reverse psychology. One day he arrived at school with a very strange-looking box which he kept suspiciously close to him throughout the day and warned everybody against opening it. This intrigued the schoolboys even more and they sneakily seized the box only to find out that the box was nothing but a prank devised by the mischievous Dashu. Dashu also voiced Ray's subtle satire towards the contemporary "Babu Culture" of Bengal in this story as he once appeared to the school in atrociously ill-fitting trousers because, as he said mockingly, he wanted to improve his English. In another incident mentioned in this story, when Dashu got told off by the teacher without having his side of the story heard because of a complaint by the sly teacher's pet Jagabandhu, he was immediately introduced to the hierarchy of the school and his position in it. As a newcomer, Dashu thought of his classmate Jagabandhu as a friendly boy and asked for his help with English. Jagabandhu, however, responded in an extremely rude manner. When Dashu pointed out his arrogance, Jagabandhu complained to the teacher and got Dashu punished. This came hardly as a surprise to the other boys of the class as they were all aware of Jagabandhu's nature and even though they were critical of his behaviour, they knew better than to provoke the teacher's pet. The "good boy" Jagabandhu was known by his classmates as an egocentric and spineless boy who would insult anybody who asked for help. However, instead of

accepting such rudeness passively as the other students, Dashu retaliated in his own humorous way. By replacing Jagabandhu's book, Dashu tricks him into getting scolded by the same teacher he used to flatter. Dashu's trick brings out the hollowness of the hierarchy of the school. The teacher's pet, who was held in high regard by the teachers and considered superior by both himself and other students, was demeaned by the teachers for something which was not his fault. This lays bare the fact that the structure that makes him feel superior to other boys does not really trust or care for him.

The futility of the seemingly ideal structure of the school is most evident in the story "Chinese Crackers." The story introduces us to a well-liked teacher who used to sleep during classes and at times would get furious with the occasional chatter of students. Because the teacher slept and did not bother the children, he was well liked by them. It is in this teacher's class that Dashu got his revenge on Ramapada, who tried to humiliate Dashu when sharing sweets. Dashu and Ramapada did not get along well. One day Ramapada brought Dashu's favourite sweets and shared them with everyone but Dashu. When he was asked to give some sweets to Dashu, he demeaned Dashu and told him he can do whatever he wants as these are his sweets. Later, Dashu hid Chinese crackers in Ramapada's container and placed them under the teacher's chair. When the crackers caused a commotion and Ramapada was blamed, Dashu accepted his mischief and justified his act with the rationale that if Ramapada had the right to humiliate Dashu for simply owning the sweets, he could also do anything with the crackers because he owned them. The teacher, on the other hand, could not say anything because he was more bothered that the other teachers might get to know that he was sleeping during his class. Ramapada symbolises those who do not use force, but rather try to subjugate people with words and mind games. The only way Dashu could have some of his favourite sweets was by acknowledging that Ramapada was superior to him. This story crystallises the role of the school as the Ideological State Apparatus. The seemingly ideal teacher sleeps in the class while the students pretend to study, thus keeping intact the façade of normalcy and status quo. The

bursting of the crackers brings pandemonium to a “perfect” order. While Dashu boldly accepts what he has done, he unintentionally ends up creating a situation where the teacher is more concerned with his reputation after being exposed for sleeping in class than punishing Dashu. No one could justify to Dashu why he was in the wrong and gave up trying, citing his madness as an excuse. This exposes their failure to make the categorical distinction between “mad” and “reasonable.” This story also serves as the best example in terms of representing the irony of Dashu’s name. The word “Dasharathi” etymologically signifies “the son of Dasharatha” pointing to Rama of the *Ramayana*. Rama was bestowed with the title “Maryada Purushottama” which refers to someone who never deviates from his duty and role. In this regard, it appears ironic that Dashu, a boy who refuses to be fixated by given roles and positions, is named after someone who vowed to be devoted to his obligations and duties .

1. Ray's illustration from “The Chinese Crackers”

2. Ray's illustration from "Dashu's Antics"

In "Dashu's Antics" the readers are introduced to a Dashu whose ridiculous bravery appears almost insane. He meticulously tricks a phony Nabinchand, who would always act full of himself and boasts about his bravery, by fabricating fake narratives about his great experiences. Dashu also takes Nabinchand's elder brother Mohanchand and his friends by surprise when he attacks the evidently stronger Mohanchand after he pulls Dashu by the ear. The boys of the school decided to stage a drama in "Dashu's Crazy Act" but chose not to include Dashu (even though he was keen to participate), for they doubted that Dashu would not follow the rules of the drama and definitely ruin it. Even though they tried their best to keep him away, Dashu tricked his way into the group by scaring away the boy playing the lead just before the final performance. Finally, he ruined the drama consciously as an act of revenge for not being chosen in the first place. In the story "The Detective," even though Dashu appears momentarily before the readers, he turns out to be the only voice of reason. While everyone suspects the new boy as the

thief, it is Dashu who speaks sense by questioning the overconfident Jaladhar, who, like the rest of the boys, believed himself to be a proficient detective. When almost the entire class assumes the new boy as the thief simply because he is new and unfamiliar, Dashu points out their irrationality by reiterating the boy's identity. Dashu saves the new boy from the ignominy of being labeled a thief by putting logic before prejudice. Even though Dashu appears for a brief period of time, he brings clarity and logic to the rest of the prejudiced class. This story hints that perhaps Dashu too is labeled as a "madcap" in a similarly unreasonable manner, as no voice of reason questions the functions of the hegemonic structure. This further reiterates the arbitrariness of the label of madness that is bestowed upon him by the prejudice of others—a label that he carries like a crown. Ray often used illustrations that added to the underlying meaning of his stories. He never illustrated the character of Dashu, but in "Chinese Crackers" and "Dashu's Antics" Ray added comic illustrations carrying not only the central idea of the stories but also the motivation behind the portrayal of his unusual protagonist. The illustrations highlight the comic disorder caused by Dashu as a locus of disruption at the centre of the structure. Dashu himself is an absent presence in both pictures—the pictures that capture the chaos caused by Dashu while he himself is physically absent from them. His ostensible absence suggests that although the structure tries to invisibilise him, he exerts agency through the chaos that scatters outward, centrifugally, from the absent centre. The first illustration shows the chaotic moment from "The Chinese Crackers" when the crackers burst under the teacher's table startling the teacher. The second picture shows Keshtha and Jagai pranking Nabinchand under Dashu's directions in the story "Dashu's Antics."

The stories imply that Dashu is not considered mad because he lacks logic or rationale, but rather because he deviates from what is normalised by the dominant structure as reason and normalcy. He is the "other" because the school as an Ideological State Apparatus labels him as the "other." When Dashu is introduced to the readers for the first

time in “Pagla Dashu,” the narrator begins with a physical description of the young boy, which differs from normative bodies. The narrator mentions that one need not be familiar with Dashu in order to recognise the madcap at a glance as his unusual physical appearance gives away his identity. “Once the school hired a new durwan who was absolutely fresh from the sticks. But even he had no trouble figuring out who Pagla Dashu was just from the mention of his name. From the way he looked, talked and walked, it was clear that Dashu was slightly touched in the head.” (Ray 2012, 1) It is, however, interesting to note that the new durwan (gatekeeper) was already told of Dashu as “pagla” [mad]. When he tried to identify Dashu, he was searching for the “mad boy,” someone who appeared a misfit in the otherwise normal surroundings and quite naturally, Dashu stood out to him. Thus, Dashu became the mad boy to the durwan even before they met. The boy with an unusual physical appearance and demeanor fit in with durwan’s idea of a mad boy. Common people like the durwan often believe in physiognomy—the physical appearance reflects the reality of the mind. Hence, if there is a misfit in the school, it must be the unusually skinny boy with a big head, round eyes, and disheveled curly hair. Just like the durwan, even the readers get introduced to Dashu with prejudiced eyes as the narrator claims to tell the story of not Dashu but Pagla (mad) Dashu. Even before his antics or tricks are mentioned, Dashu is already established as a “madcap,” and all of his subsequent actions are judged, by both the other characters of the stories and the readers, through the tinted glasses of prejudice. Thus, Dasharathi becomes Pagla Dashu (Mad Dashu) not simply because of his own actions but rather because others label him as mad. It is this labeling of Dashu as the mad boy that tries to establish his position as the marginal “other” in the hierarchical structure of the school.

According to Michel Foucault, one of the ways the madman has been alienated throughout history is through the sudden realisation of his own position as the stranger in his own place, his own situation. Ray’s Dashu is not only aware of how he is perceived by others but also can

manipulate and ridicule the title “mad” bestowed upon him. In the story “Pagla Dashu” the narrator says that students would often make unkind comments about Dashu’s physical appearance and mental faculties upfront, to which Dashu did not take offense, but rather “would add colour to our comments and relate bizarre stories about himself.” (Ray 2012, 3) When some students tried to make fun of Dashu’s thin and tall physique by comparing him to a scarecrow, Dashu jokingly chipped in by commenting that people would often call him to substitute for a scarecrow because of his identical appearance. He often appears to be admirably at peace with himself. He can make fun of himself as he is not insecure about his “strangeness,” and he refuses to accept the inferior position conferred upon him. In fact, he further goes on to exploit his image as the “mad” boy when he pranks his classmates with his mysterious box in the same story. He never once asked them to look into the box but rather advised against it. However, he was aware of their insatiable curiosity regarding the “mad boy,” and there he had the upper hand to trick them. It should always be remembered that Dashu is not the “other” because he is excluded. In fact, had he actually been excluded from this hegemonic hierarchy of the school, he would have been beyond the contention of “self” and “other” and would not be controlled by the structure. Dashu is the “other” because the structure refuses to exclude him and forcefully situates him at the margin. He is included only to be kept as marginalised as it is the existence of the margin that affirms the existence of the centre. The “self” needs to fix the “other” within but closer to the margin in order to perpetuate its own place at the center. In this case, the mad “other” is created to uphold the sane “self.” However, Dashu does not passively accept his tag as the marginalised “other” but rather manipulates this label. His shenanigans could have caused him serious punishment otherwise, but as the narrator puts it, “Dashu got away with it because he was ‘mad.’” (Ray 2012, 4)

If analysed carefully, it would be apparent that Dashu is somewhat successful in subverting the status quo and asserting power over the structure that tries to tame him. Asma Ladha mentions that the

structure ostracises Dashu by refusing him any sort of punishment for his ill behavior as it believes him to be beyond redemption. No matter how hard Dashu tries for his position to be acknowledged by attracting everybody's attention through his tomfoolery, the mad boy's existence is not considered serious enough to be a part of society's law and order. This article debates Ladha's argument. Ray uses madness as a tool not to ostracise but rather to empower Dashu and grant him freedom within the confining ideological structure of the school. Ray never lets Dashu get trampled by the center-margin binaries. In fact, when the structure tries to throw him toward the margin, he forces his way toward the center and jumbles up the structure itself. This is most evidently indicated in "Dashu's Crazy Act" where even though everyone refuses Dashu a part in the play, Dashu tricks his way in. Not only does he play his part, but also takes his revenge against those trying to silence him by inventing lines and ruining the entire play. The success of a play depends largely upon how well one can play the role one is given, as the failure to stick to the designated role disrupts the structure of the play. Dashu never limits himself to the circumscribed role provided to him that would maintain the structure, neither on stage nor in real life. The very discourse that tries to silence him in return gets subverted by him. Had madness been used to ostracise Dashu, his acts would not have evoked doubt among other students such as the narrator. It would have never led to a questioning of the idea of madness itself, and neither would Dashu be able to wreak havoc within the structure. In *History of Madness* (2006) Foucault argues that rationalism suppresses the language of madness thereby condemning it to silence. (Foucault 2006, xxviii) Dashu cannot be silenced as he always outshines the dominant discourse that makes every possible attempt to subalternise him. He is not an inert, helpless victim in a cruel society waiting to be heard, but rather a principle of rebellion and resistance that always makes its own voice impossible to ignore. However, whatever outlandish act Dashu commits, he is excused from punishment as he is believed to be mad. This paper accepts Ladha's claim that society does not punish Dashu as it believes him to be beyond redemption but takes a step further to insist

that Dashu turns this into an opportunity for further subversive actions. The very ideology that aimed to restrain him accidentally ends up granting him freedom within the same system.

In most works of Nonsense Literature, madness and disorderliness are portrayed as necessary conditions of “becoming.” Even in Lewis Carroll’s *Alice’s Adventures in Wonderland* (1865), Alice must go through madness in order to fully understand herself and the society around her. Ray, an ardent admirer of Carroll, takes this concept further. Dashu’s madness does not stop at providing knowledge, but rather gives him a certain power and the possibility of self-actualisation. In all the stories that include Dashu, madness becomes very important, as besides constituting his identity, it also shows the fractures of the underlying politics of madness. Against the strictures of the dominant structure, Dashu uses his madness as a tool to make a hodge-podge of the system while being in it and to enable him to get away with the chaos afterward. Dashu, who “could not sing to save his life—he had no sense of melody or rhythm and he knew this very well,” started singing vehemently when the school inspector visited. (Ray 2012, 4) Rhythm in music represents a well-defined structure that binds the whole musical piece together. Even a slight deviation from this would cause the entire musical piece to become disarrayed and get ruined. Similarly, the school presents a hegemonic structure, and Dashu’s audacity to turn such an important ceremony of the visit of the school inspector, someone who is at the top of the hierarchy, into a carnivalesque situation indeed disrupts the rhythm or order of such an important occasion. According to Althusser, power cannot be gained and exercised until it is held over and through the Ideological State Apparatus. Arguably, Dashu successfully achieves this power as he not only disrupts the order of the institution that tries to limit him from within the structure but also makes other students question the very idea of madness. Through antics such as humiliating the teacher’s pet Jagabandhu, pranking arrogant Nabinchand and Ramapada, or tearing open the facade of the seemingly ideal sleeping school teacher, Dashu turns this structure upside down thereby urging the students to doubt if Dashu actually is a mad boy or just an ingenious trickster.

In her article, Ladha asserts that the cruelty of Dashu's society lies in the fact that Dashu's madness is imposed upon him simply to turn him into a ridiculous laughingstock. (p.18) This claim can be countered with the argument that Pagla Dashu, the mad "other" of the school, wreaks havoc on the order of the school providing the possibility of a counter to the dominant discourse of madness. Foucault explains that madness can appear only within the social context as oppression and exclusion cannot be without the existence of society. (p.131) The hierarchic structure of the school appears almost as a microcosm of the macrocosmic social structure. Within the hegemonic design of the school, those at the bottom of the structure operate under a constant cloud of fear and intimidation, which restrains them, and elides the possibility of opposing injustice even when it is evident. In the story "Dashu's Antics," the arrogant show-off Nabinchand and his elder brother Mohanchand are not confronted because of their seeming superiority. When people pose some doubt about Nabinchand's narrative of him being wounded by some dacoits, Nabinchand manages to make them trust him owing to his authoritative stance that intimidates others. Even physically stronger Kestha fears confronting a weaker Nabinchand simply because he feels Nabinchand might get him into trouble. Dashu not only has the courage to expose the meekness of Nabinchand and fight Mohanchand but also has the intelligence to trick greedy Keshtha and Jagai who would agree to beat just anyone for some sweets. Dashu does not care even when he is punished and continues to laugh at the thought of how the spineless Nabinchand made a fool of himself. Even the older and stronger Mohanchand is bewildered seeing Dashu's courage to fight back if attacked. At the end of the story, the narrator seems to voice everybody's doubt, including that of the reader, about whether Dashu really is a mad boy. Dashu was earlier described as follows: "It was not as if he was dim-witted. He was clever at maths, especially in solving long divisions and multiplications. Then again he would devise such ingenious tricks to make fools of us that we could only marvel at his brains." (Ray, 2012, 2) Through Dashu, Ray makes the school boys as well as the readers question the hierarchies and binaries,

doubt the “natural” marginal position of the madman, and be critical of the generally celebrated valuation of reason over madness. Across the corpus of the Dashu stories, it becomes clear that the narrator and his friends are often almost astonished by the genius of Dashu’s mind. “Normal” characters fail to successfully argue with him, as he cannot be reasoned with the limited terms of their logic. Thus, Dashu “the mad boy” often appears as a reasonable person who is at peace with his sense of values and ideals.

Madness often appears to provide the scope of an alternative discourse that questions or goes against the dominant ideology or power structure while being situated within it. Be it Hamlet’s feigned madness or Ophelia’s real one, Lady Macbeth’s sleepwalking scene, or King Lear’s madness, it becomes evident to a critical eye that in all these cases madness stands in opposition to or is critical of the hegemonic power structure. In twentieth-century Bengal, besides carrying the connotation of mental instability, there was also the alternative popular belief of the madman having prophetic qualities. The saintly madmen were celebrated for receiving divine wisdom beyond the comprehension of common people. Such a saint was believed to diverge from the ways of the common man because of the elevated consciousness that relieved him from the constraints of the social conventions of regular people. (Morinis Year?, 985) In contemporary Bengali literature, the idea of madness was often used to question and criticise society and nation. For example, in the works of Rabindranath Tagore, the madman often appears as either the wisest person who is popularly misunderstood for deviating from the dominant discourse, or the victim who has succumbed to constricting social ideologies. Nonsense literature presents the idea of madness as an essential requirement for achieving freedom and agency—the fundamental tool to question, problematise, and even resist the dominant social and ideological confinement. Apart from the connotations of the word “madness” in terms of a mental illness, as found in the field of psychiatry, another popular use of the word is to denote abnormal and often chaotic behaviour. Such an idea

carries along with it an intricate question—what is the “normal” that this madness deviates from? This highlights the political undertones of the use of the term “madness.” Analysing Sukumar Ray’s works, Rima Chakraborty argues that Ray’s nonsense is what might be described as “metasense” because it effectively reestablishes the importance of satire as a medium of social commentary. His works offer a different understanding of logic and reason in an effort to spark the emergence of political consciousness laying bare the operations of the forces that establish the acceptability of logic and reason. (p.108) Thus, in Ray’s world, the mad person appears to be someone who refuses to unquestionably accept what is dictated as being normal. Sukumar Ray’s understanding of madness is perhaps best exemplified in his “The Drawing,” another short story in *The Crazy Tales of Pagla Dashu and Co.* Kalachand is a young boy who draws a picture that others refuse to understand. They misinterpret his art and advise him on how he could turn it into something else, something meaningful. The other characters in the story fail to comprehend Kalachand’s perspective and, instead of trying to accept his ideas, impose their own views and “meaning” upon his works. When he gets frustrated about being misunderstood and silenced, he is termed mad for his “absurd” anger. People are so obsessed with what the drawing “could or should be” that they turn a blind eye to what it “already is.” Kalachand gets punished by the teacher because his violent outburst is unreasonable and insane. This story exhibits the politics behind the production of “meaning” or “reason” as stagnant points within a structure and what grants them legitimacy. Kalachand is not “mad” because he lacks reason or vision, he is “mad” because others fail and refuse to comprehend his sense of “meaning” and “reason” which differs from their own. Ray understands madness as something that is conferred upon one by others rather than something essential and innate. Similarly, it can be argued that Pagla Dashu is labeled as mad not for something inherently “mad” about him but rather because others think he is mad. However, unlike Kalachand, the trickster Dashu tricks his way in refusing to conform and keep his position fluid within the hierarchy.

Dashu, a young “madcap,” brings in the chaotic force of resistance within the repressive structure of his school—one that mirrors contemporary schools in Ray’s times. At a point in Indian history when schools and other educational institutions were going through massive reformation, Ray’s work reveals how social institutions introduced a hierarchical structure that largely aligned with the ideological frame of the dominant class to children. Children, being indoctrinated to submit to their position in the structure, rarely questioned the ideology and often accepted the ideological and social framework as absolute. Through Dashu, Ray satirises the hierarchical order formed within the school and points at the arbitrariness of the power structure and labels that operate as markers of identity. Dashu’s conflict is not against “self” or “other” but rather against the ideological structure that constitutes such binaries and naturalises them. Throughout the stories, Ray highlights the growing confusion among his friends regarding the authenticity of Dashu’s madness. He acts insane while questioning and disregarding the order which is otherwise unequivocally accepted by other students and teachers, and it is at times like these that Dashu almost appears as the most “reasonable” person. Thus, he keeps switching between absolute chaos and order, reason and absurdity, and margin and center. Dashu has no fixed nature either. Just when he is about to be termed as an egoistic prankster or unreasonable fool, he does something heroic and intelligent. He cannot be tagged as the hero who is absolutely good or the rascal who loves disorder. It is impossible to chain him to one place or position. It is this liminal state that the dominant discourse likes to term “madness” as it cannot shackle Dashu to a restrictive label. Thus, it is this madness and the consciousness of the operations of such a tag that enables his mobility anywhere within the structure. Only in this liminal space can the possibility of liberation exist. M. J. Matušík argues that “the subjects of liberation live at a border” and it is this madness that grants Dashu the marginal position and his consciousness of it. (p.114) Thus, madness becomes the necessary condition for his liberation as the very madness that renders Dashu the “other” empowers him to strike the structure from within.

The theme of resistance against the hegemonic design of educational institutions is not new in Bengali literature and one of the finest examples of this can be found in works by Rabindranath Tagore. Especially in his *Achalayatan: the Petrified Palace* (2006), Tagore puts forward the frailty of the institution named Achalayatan and its obsession with confining minds to existing practices. It refuses any scope of doubt and the students must unquestionably abide by the age-old practices of education. Achalayatan, which literally translates to “immobile manor,” portrays how the dogmatic system of institutions can confine and pollute young minds making them scared or critical of free thinking. By the end of Tagore’s play, the hegemonic structure of Achalayatan is demolished, and an open-minded and liberating atmosphere is deemed as the necessary condition for acquiring knowledge. Tagore shows that true madness is unquestionably accepting and rigidly sticking to ideologies and suggests that one must liberate oneself from such insanity. The institution Ray presents is not, however, as cruel, rigid, and polarised as Achalayatan. (Roy) In fact, there is no outright evil character in Dashu’s world. Unlike the protagonist of Tagore’s play, Dashu is not the upright hero who liberates everyone. Neither are the teachers as stubbornly dogmatic or the other students as passive and naively unaware of the power structure. While there are strict and seemingly unreasonable teachers as found in “Pagla Dashu,” there are also kind and empathetic souls. Even though the boys poke fun at Dashu, none of them are outright hostile to him. While there are hierarchies, quarrels, tricks, and punishments, there is no hatred. Characters in Dashu’s world do not need a hero to save them from the suffocating structure. Dashu, without any such grandiose ambitions, simply makes them aware of the arbitrariness of power structures, and they themselves think through or question the prison of ideology. The villain, thus, is not people but rather the function of the Ideological State Apparatus for the benefit of the dominant class. In Ray’s world the “other” is never utterly despised, nor is the “self” idealised. Dashu’s structure criticises all while being kind to all as the subject of critique is the structure itself and not those who are a part of it. Those within the

system are unaware of how the structure confines them to fixed roles. Hence, Ray's Dashu never hurts anyone without a cause, simply out of whimsical "madness," or because he has an unlikely kind of power acquired by being conscious of the workings of the structure. Thus, while Dashu's madness gives him a superior position to question and criticise the politics of order and normalcy, he is also the adorable boy who gives the readers a hearty laugh while also enjoying the biting edge of Ray's satire.

NOTES

1. Sukumar Ray (1887-1923) is one of the most celebrated authors of children's literature in India. Ray has created a legacy in Bengali satire and nonsense literature. He is also considered a pioneer in illustration and printmaking in contemporary India. Pagla Dashu is one of Ray's most celebrated characters who appeared in some of his short stories published in *Sandesh*, the Bengali magazine published by the famous Ray family for children. Ray classified his works as a product of "Kheyal Rasa," the affective element of whim or fancy.

2. Pagla Dashu ("pagla" meaning "mad" in Bengali and "Dashu" is the short form of the name "Dasharathi") is one of the most famous creations of Sukumar Ray. Dashu appeared in a few of Ray's Bengali short stories during the early twentieth century, in the periodical *Sandesh* and later was included in a short story collection with the title *Pagla Dashu*. In 2012 scholars from Jadavpur University translated the collection and published *The Crazy Tales of Pagla Dashu and Co.*

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